

Exploring the Effectiveness of RePlanet: a Board Game Approach to Climate Change Education

Table 1. Answers to Closed-Ended Knowledge Questions

Question	Mean correctness			Standard deviation		
	Pre-game	Post-game	Change	Pre-game	Post-game	Change
1. Can you, by yourself, bring to zero your emissions of polluting gasses?	55%	63%	+9%	22%	22%	0
2. Is it possible to solve climate change by the next two years?	60%	68%	+8%	20%	19%	-1%
3. Does a single solution exist which, by itself, can solve climate change?	63%	67%	+4%	20%	18%	-2%
4. Can the wealthiest countries, by themselves, solve climate change?	48%	64%	+6%	22%	24%	+2%
5. Can the poorest countries, by themselves, solve climate change?	66%	74%	+8%	16%	14%	-2%
6. Can technology, by itself, solve climate change?	50%	55%	+5%	21%	23%	+2%
7. Does climate change increase the number of threatened populations?	83%	90%	+7%	17%	13%	-4%
8. Can supporting natural systems help to solve climate change?	84%	85%	+2%	14%	17%	+3%
9. In the following list, which are the two market sectors with the worst environmental impact? — Energy production, Farming and livestock, Manufacturing, Transportation, Construction.	20%	58%	+38%	12%	17%	+5%
Average	59%	68%	+9%	18%	18%	0

Table 2. Answers to Open-Ended Question about the Critical Factors Hindering a Solution to Climate Change

Thematic cluster	Pre-game Answers	Pre-game Rank	Post-game Answers	Post-game Rank	Change Answers	Change Rank
Lack of cooperation	22	1	26	1	+4	0
Cultural or psychological factors	17	2	12	3	-5	-1
Unwillingness for lifestyle changes	17	2	8	4	-9	-2
Economical factors	11	4	15	2	+4	+2
Lack of information	11	4	8	4	-3	0
Unavailability of solutions	8	6	2	10	-6	-4
Insufficient time	3	7	7	6	+4	+1
Demographic factors	2	8	3	8	+1	-1
Difficulty of balancing sustainability and well-being	1	9	4	8	+3	+1
Complexity	0	10	5	7	+5	+3

Table 3. Post-Game Survey (Likert's Scale)

Question	Mean	Standard deviation
1. <i>I would like to play this game again</i>	4.43	0.77
2. <i>I would like to play this kind of game more, also on other topics</i>	4.63	0.86
3. <i>I would like to play this game also outside school</i>	3.62	1.00
4. <i>During the game I had difficulty understanding the rules</i>	3.44	0.96
5. <i>During the game there were some moments when I was not sure which was the right choice to make</i>	2.83	1.05
6. <i>I think I would be able to play this game even without an expert helping me</i>	2.93	1.23
7. <i>By playing this game I have learned new things on climate change</i>	3.95	0.95
8. <i>I would like to show this game to my friends</i>	3.60	1.20
9. <i>If I played this game with my friends, I think they would learn new things on climate change</i>	3.80	0.98
10. <i>I think that if I played this game again I would understand better the topics the game is about</i>	4.63	0.62

Table 4. Experience and Usability Survey

Question	Thematic cluster	Number of answers
11. <i>What did you like most about the game?</i>	Cooperation	24
	Strategic thinking	6
	The theme of climate change	3
	Others (less than 2 answers each)	7
12. <i>What did you like least about the game?</i>	Difficulty of the rules	11
	Communities in crisis	5
	Adverse effects	4
	Difficulty of achieving the objective	4
	Others (less than 3 answers each)	19
13. <i>What do you think you have learned from the game?</i>	Notions on climate change	20
	Importance of cooperation	16
	Difficulty of balancing sustainability and well-being of communities	7
	Others (less than 3 answers each)	10
14. <i>What did you find most difficult to understand in the game?</i>	Rules	31
	Communities in crisis	5
	Emissions and well-being	3
	Others (less than 2 answers each)	3